

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL - 4

PARTICIPATION CONSENT

Please Note: The ethical considerations were taken as a part of the dissertation project with a different title.

The consent for collecting the data from the respected schools of both the study areas, was taken from the Principal and the Head Master of the schools. For collecting the data in Delhi, the Principal agreed on the basis that the confidential information of the children won't be revealed and so personal questions were to be asked by the students. The application Performa for collecting the information from the school was given by the Institution. The image of the same has been attached below.

REF No. *10481001*
Dated *06.10.2022*

CENTRE FOR PUBLIC HEALTH
Panjab University, Chandigarh (160014)
(Institute for Emerging Areas in Science & Technology)

DR. SAVITA PRASHAR
COORDINATOR

Ph: 0172-2541441 Ext.6192
Email: - cphpu@pu.ac.in

The Principal
S.P.M. Sarvodya Co-ed Vidyalaya
Chittranjan Park
New Delhi

Sir/Madam,

This is to kindly inform you that our student Ms. Ritika Kapoor is a bonafide student of MPH 2nd Year in Centre for Public Health, Panjab University, Chandigarh. She is doing research on **“Healthy eating intervention for analysing nutritional knowledge in middle school children of Delhi and Chandigarh”**. She intends to visit S.P.M. Sarvodya Co-ed Vidyalaya, Chittranjan Park, New Delhi to collect the data for research purpose. Information collected shall be used for academic purpose only and kept confidential.

Thanking You

Regards
S Prashar

(Dr. Savita Prashar)
CoorCoordinator
Centre for Public Health
IEAST
Panjab University,
Chandigarh

Figure (a): Consent form For Delhi study area.

For collecting the data in Chandigarh, the permission was taken from the District education Department, after submitting the required documents. Then, the Headmaster agreed only on the basis that the confidential information of the children won't be revealed and so personal questions were to be asked by the students. The image of the same has been attached below.

OFFICE OF THE DISTRICT EDUCATION OFFICER, SECTOR-19, UT, CHANDIGARH

ORDER

Permission is hereby granted to Ms. Ritika Kapoor, Research Scholar, Centre for public health, Panjab University, Sector-14, Chandigarh to collect data for thesis entitled as "Healthy eating intervention for analyzing nutritional knowledge in middle school children of Delhi and Chandigarh" from students of class 5th to 8th of following Govt. Schools, Chandigarh with the condition that the study will be done only with the consent of the Principal/Head of the school(s) without disturbing the normal working of the school, no financial implication is involved, personal information of the students will be given and the data collected from the research will not be shared with anyone:-

S.No.	Name of the School
1.	Govt. Model High School, Sector-25, Chd.
2.	Govt. Model Sr. Sec. School, Sector-16, Chd.

Dated, Chd. the
03.05.2023

BINDU ARORA
DISTRICT EDUCATION OFFICER
UT, CHANDIGARH.

Endst. No. DEO/UT/E5/2023/ 12055-58 Dated: 04/5/23

A copy is forwarded to the following for information and necessary action:-

1. The Director School Education, Chandigarh Administration.
2. The Heads of concerned Govt. Schools, UT, Chandigarh. The study will be done only with your consent. It must ensure that there is no financial implication, normal working of the school is not disturbed and personal information of the student will not be given to any outsider.
3. The Coordinator, Centre for Public Health, Panjab University, Sector-14, Chandigarh w.r.t. memo no.1079/CPH dated 20.04.2023.
4. Ms Ritika Kapoor, Research Scholar, Centre for Public Health, Panjab University, Sector-14, Chandigarh. It is requested to submit an undertaking to the Head that the information will be used for research only and without the permission of the department, it will not be given/ forwarded to anyone.

Superintendent Estt.,
for District Education Officer,
Chandigarh.

4/5/23

Figure (b): Consent form For Chandigarh study area.